

ISic3376

I.Sicily inscription 3376

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Hybla Heraea

Place of origin (modern)

Ragusa

Provenance

From tomb 15 of the archaic necropolis in contrada Cuciniello/Cucinello, excavated by Orsi in 1898, vicinity of Ragusa station

Coordinates

36.915712, 14.729270

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 19047

Physical Description

Upper left corner of a large slab, broken on right and below, with a recessed moulding on the left edge. Orsi speculates could have been part of a cippus covering a tomb.

Dimensions

Height 40 cm

Width 70 cm

Depth 28 cm

Layout

Remains of a single line of large Greek letters

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Γοστιφο[---]

Apparatus

Text after Arena 1998

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645604

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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